

Human-centred breakthrough technologies for a safer and greener construction industry

The consortium of **HumanTech** — “Human-centred technologies for a safer and greener European construction industry” — is proud to announce this ambitious and innovative initiative, funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, has officially begun.

The **European construction industry** faces three major challenges: increase the safety and wellbeing of its workforce, improve its productivity, and become greener, making efficient use of resources.

To address these challenges, HumanTech proposes to develop **human-centred cutting-edge technologies** such as wearables for workers' safety and support and robots that can harmoniously coexist with human workers while contributing to the ecological transition of the sector.

HumanTech aims to achieve major advances in cutting-edge technologies that will enable a safe, rewarding and digital work environment for a new generation of highly skilled construction workers and engineers.

These advances will include:

- **Robotic devices equipped with vision and intelligence** that allow them to navigate autonomously and safely in highly unstructured environments, collaborate with humans and dynamically update a semantic digital twin of the construction site in which they are.
- **Smart, unobtrusive workers protection and support equipment.** From exoskeletons activated by body sensors for posture and strain to wearable cameras and XR glasses that provide real-time workers' location and guidance for them to perform their tasks efficiently and accurately.
- An entirely new breed of **Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins (DSDTs) of construction sites** that simulate in detail the current state of a construction

site at the geometric and semantic level, based on an extended Building Information Modeling (BIM) formulation that contains all relevant structural and semantic dimensions (BIMxD). BIMxDs will act as a common reference for all human workers, engineers and autonomous machines.

To this end, the HumanTech project aims to **exploit synergies with ongoing EU projects in the BIM/DigitalTwin area** and support further advancing these technologies.

The **HumanTech** consortium is formed by **22 organisations** — leading research institutes and universities, innovative hi-tech SMEs and large enterprises, construction groups and a construction SME representative — from **10 countries**, bringing **expertise in 11 different disciplines**. The consortium is led by the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence's Augmented Vision department.

Learn more about HumanTech and contact us!

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